

Patient - Emily Trinidad (they/them)

"I want a way to quickly and authentically connect with mental health providers and peers who face the same issues, to reduce my anxiety about the future."

Bio

Emily is the eldest of four children. Emily's parents, immigrants, both work and stress the importance of education. They were an overachiever in high school and the first in their family to attend university. Emily feels pressure to make their parents proud and to set a good example for their younger siblings. Emily chose not to stay on campus, living with their family to save money and to help their parents and siblings. They feel stressed about safety on campus and in the city and world events but feel powerless to change things. They worry about money; school, work, and home responsibilities leave little time for fun and Emily often feels lonely or cut off from friends.

Emily works hard on time management so that they can complete college with good grades. Emily works 20 hours a week and considers this the only time to hang out with friends. They do not sleep as much as they need or would like. Until Emily sought help for depression and anxiety, visits to medical professionals were limited to the occasional check-up or serious illness. Emily now prioritizes visits to a therapist on campus every other week.

Education: Bachelor's degree in Business (in progress, sophomore); considering change to art

Years of experience: 1

Work location: Moves between school and work as a barista

Health Conditions

- In good physical health, but has recently been diagnosed with anxiety and depression
- Covered on mother's health insurance
- Emily finds their own providers, makes their own appointments

Healthcare influences

- Emily had regular childhood medical check-ups. Their mother managed their healthcare, and their father approved their mother's decisions
- Family members initially dismissed Emily's depression symptoms because their family does not believe in mental health issues as an illness
- The ease with which their friends share their mental health experiences and struggles have normalized therapy

Goals

- Emily wants to manage their stress and anxiety so they can be productive at school, work, and life
- Emily wants to obtain virtual access to healthcare providers
- Emily wants online scheduling and the ability to text questions to their provider

Software attitude & use

- At ease with technology but prefers face-to-face interactions, to make what they consider to be more authentic connections.
- Uses a smartphone and laptop to manage their healthcare
- Social media: YouTube, Instagram, TikTok. Like many in Gen Z, they strongly prefer visual content over written content

Opportunities to connect

- Mobile apps are important to reaching Emily
- Integrate existing tools, like Instagram, into websites for patients like Emily, to share authoritative yet personal and engaging information
- Provide easier and more flexible scheduling tools. Emily wants to see last minute cancellations and book 'on the fly'

Wants/Needs

- **Respect.** Providers who are considerate about age and gender identity and use their pronoun
- **Connection.** Health care providers who listen, care, are available to help
- **Credible information.** Help evaluating medical information for authority, accuracy, and bias. Emily is busy with school, with no time to do extensive research
- **Meaningful content.** Video content about resources to cope with depression and anxiety
- **Access.** Flexible night/weekend appointments; personal connections with doctors via social media

Support Network

Emily's mother and friends are their main supporters. They say there were periods during their freshman year when 'they could have used more support'

Friends support Emily during the day through texts, TikTok, or Instagram, or through in-person interactions at their workplace

Would like to use mobile medication or therapy apps, but can't afford the fees

Emily needs additional support. They want tools to connect them with other college students who deal with anxiety and depression